

Kinetics and Mechanisms of Exchange Reactions. In (III) Ethylenediaminetetraacetate— Fe^{3+} and Ga (III) Ethylenediaminetetraacetate— Fe^{3+} Systems

RADHA R. DAS

Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Chemistry Division, Trombay, Bombay-85.

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Kinetic data for the metal complex-metal exchange reactions involving In (III) ethylenediaminetetraacetate (In EDTA, InY)- Fe^{3+} , and GaEDTA- Fe^{3+} in perchloric acid were evaluated by the spectrophotometric technique. A possible mechanism of the exchange is proposed. The reaction rate is first order with respect to the concentration of the complex as well as the attacking ion. The exchange is very slow in weakly acid solutions, but fast in the range 0.1-0.3M acid. The rate constant is directly proportional to the square of the hydrogen ion concentration and inversely proportional to the displaced ion. The rate constant for the exchange of the gallium complex at any particular $[\text{H}^+]$ is smaller than that for the indium.

The mechanism proposed involves a rapid preequilibration of the diprotonated complex which dissociates into the metal ion and the ligand in a steady state equilibrium process. This process eventually determines the rate of the overall reaction. The slower rate of the gallium complex exchange, in spite of its lesser thermodynamic stability compared to the indium complex, is explained on the basis of its smaller rate of dissociation.

A large amount of data is now available, particularly in acid medium, for the metal complex-metal exchange reactions involving the divalent metal ions¹⁻⁸ of the first row transition elements. We had undertaken exchange reactions involving cobalt ethylenediaminetetraacetate (CoEDTA, CoY) with Ni^{2+} in weakly acid environments⁹ to study the details of the mechanism in this exchange reaction. From the measured overall rate constants, those for the acid independent and the acid dependent paths of the mechanism had been determined. The hydrogen ion independent path had been compared with the binuclear (M-Y-M') transient intermediate species proposed by Margerum et al⁷ for similar systems. In order to check the applicability of this mechanism at higher pHs we extended the study to the exchange of CuEDTA and CuHEDTA with Ni^{2+} in alkaline region¹⁰. The problem of precipitation of the metal ions was controlled by keeping the system in ammoniacal

medium. From the stability constants of the mixed complexes of metal EDTA-ligand, as well as the unwrapped segments, with NH_3 , it was possible to predict and compare the reaction rates of these two systems.

Relatively few references are available on exchange reactions of rapidly reacting trivalent metal ion (having closed shell configuration) complex systems¹¹, presumably because of the possible complications of their easy hydrolysis and polymerization. It was, therefore, the purpose of this investigation to study the kinetics of exchange of reactions involving InEDTA and GaEDTA with ferric ion.

Experimental :

The stock solutions ($\sim 0.1M$) of indium, gallium and iron were prepared in 0.2M perchloric acid to prevent hydrolysis. The exchange reaction was started by mixing $10^{-5}M$ solutions of the complex and of Fe^{3+} . The reaction was followed by

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measuring the absorbance of the ferric complex on a Beckman Du Spectrophotometer.

Results :

InEDTA - Fe³⁺ system :

For the overall reaction

(where the suffix T indicates total concentration)

Kinetic measurements were made at various concentrations of the reactants, displaced ion and acid. In the range 5×10^{-4} to 4×10^{-3} M, the reaction rate was first order with respect to the concentration of InEDTA as well as of Fe³⁺, therefore, second order on the whole. The rate of the backward reaction was immeasurably slow for identical conditions. Hence the rate constants were directly determined from the second order plots. Such rate constants (k_0) obtained for various initial concentrations of the reactants, displaced ion and hydrogen ion concentration are summarized in Table 1. The reaction rate

Fig. 1. Plots of k_0 vs $[\text{H}^+]^2$ for InY-Fe³⁺ and GaY-Fe³⁺ systems.

System	Temp.
(1) InY	25°C
(2) InY	40°C
(3) GaY	30°C
(4) GaY	40°C

TABLE 1 - EXCHANGE OF INEDTA - Fe³⁺ SYSTEM. TEMPERATURE - 25°, $\mu = 0.5$ M

[InY], 10 ⁻³ M	[Fe ³⁺], 10 ⁻³ M	[In ³⁺], 10 ⁻³ M	[H ⁺]	k_0 , 10 ⁻² M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
1.0	3.0	0.0	0.20	42.0
1.0	2.0	0.0	0.20	42.0
1.0	1.0	0.0	0.20	45.3
1.0	0.5	0.0	0.20	42.5
3.0	1.0	0.0	0.20	43.3
0.5	1.0	0.0	0.20	42.5
1.0	1.0	0.4	0.20	26.7
1.0	1.0	0.8	0.20	15.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	0.20	11.6
1.0	1.0	2.0	0.20	6.6
1.0	1.0	0.2	0.10	7.5
1.0	1.0	0.2	0.125	10.8
1.0	1.0	0.2	0.15	17.5
1.0	1.0	0.2	0.18	26.7
1.0	1.0	0.2	0.20	32.0
1.0	1.0	0.4	0.10	5.5
1.0	1.0	0.4	0.125	9.2
1.0	1.0	0.4	0.150	13.3
1.0	1.0	0.4	0.175	16.7
1.0	1.0	0.4	0.20	25.0

was inversely dependent on [In³⁺] and directly on the square of the [H⁺]. Plots of k_0 against $[\text{H}^+]^2$ was a straight line passing through the origin (Fig. 1), indicating that the contribution from any [H⁺] independent path is negligible.

GaEDTA - Fe³⁺ system :

The rate constants obtained for various initial concentrations of GaY, Fe³⁺, Ga³⁺ and H⁺ are summarized in Table 2. The dependence of the

TABLE 2 - EXCHANGE OF GAEDTA - Fe³⁺ SYSTEM. TEMPERATURE - 30°, $\mu = 0.5$

[GaY], 10 ⁻³ M	[Fe ³⁺], 10 ⁻³ M	[Ga ³⁺], 10 ⁻³ M	[H ⁺]	k_0 , 10 ⁻² M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
1.0	3.0	0.0	0.15	6.7
1.0	1.0	0.0	0.15	7.0
3.0	1.0	0.0	0.15	7.0
0.8	1.0	0.0	0.15	7.0
1.0	1.0	0.25	0.15	6.7
1.0	1.0	0.50	0.15	6.0
1.0	1.0	0.80	0.15	4.1
1.0	1.0	1.0	0.15	3.3
1.0	1.0	2.0	0.15	2.0
1.0	1.0	4.0	0.15	1.1
1.0	1.0	0.25	0.10	5.0
1.0	1.0	0.25	0.15	10.6
1.0	1.0	0.25	0.20	17.6
1.0	1.0	0.25	0.25	26.3
1.0	1.0	0.50	0.10	4.0
1.0	1.0	0.50	0.15	6.7
1.0	1.0	0.50	0.20	10.0
1.0	1.0	0.50	0.25	14.7
1.0	1.0	0.50	0.27	20.0

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